

The Relationships Between Job Satisfaction and Work Role Function, Stress, Quality-of-Life of Blue-Collar and White-Collar Workers with Structural Equation Modeling

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Abstract: Job satisfaction is a critical factor influencing employee well-being and productivity. However, the underlying factors may differ across occupational groups. In order to enhance workplace outcomes, it is essential to understand how work role function, stress, and quality of life impact job satisfaction in both blue-collar and white-collar workers. With structural equation modeling, we investigated the relationships between job satisfaction and work role function, stress, and quality of life for blue-collar and white-collar workers. We conducted interviews with 175 blue-collar and 162 white-collar workers. The Short Form-12 health survey (SF-12), Perceived Stress Scale (PSS), Work Role Function Questionnaire (WRFQ), and Minnesota Satisfaction Questionnaire (MSQ) were performed. As a result of the structural equation model, mental quality of life increased WRFQ and decreased PSS, and physical quality of life increased WRFQ in both groups. In addition, WRFQ increased job satisfaction in blue-collar workers, and PSS decreased job satisfaction in white-collar workers. We conclude that job satisfaction is affected by work role function in blue-collar workers and job stress in white-collar workers.

Keywords: Job satisfaction, Quality of life, Job-related stress, Workers, Employees.

As Relações entre a Satisfação no Trabalho e a Função no Trabalho, o Stress e a Qualidade de Vida dos Trabalhadores de Colarinho Azul e Branco com Modelação de Equações Estruturais

Resumo: A satisfação no trabalho é um fator crítico que influencia o bem-estar e a produtividade dos colaboradores. No entanto, os fatores subjacentes podem diferir entre grupos profissionais. Para melhorar os resultados no local de trabalho, é essencial compreender como a função profissional, o stress e a qualidade de vida têm impacto na satisfação no trabalho, tanto nos trabalhadores de colarinho azul como nos de colarinho branco. Com a modelação de equações estruturais, investigámos as relações entre a satisfação no trabalho e a função no trabalho, o stress e a qualidade de vida para os trabalhadores de colarinho azul e branco. Realizámos entrevistas a 175 operários e 162 trabalhadores administrativos. Foram realizados o inquérito de saúde Short Form-12 (SF-12), a Escala de Stress Percecionado (PSS), o Questionário de Função no Trabalho (WRFQ) e o Questionário de Satisfação de Minnesota (MSQ). Como resultado do modelo de equações estruturais, a qualidade de vida mental aumentou o WRFQ e diminuiu o PSS, e a qualidade de vida física aumentou o WRFQ em ambos os grupos. Além disso, o WRFQ aumentou a satisfação profissional dos trabalhadores administrativos e o PSS diminuiu a satisfação profissional dos trabalhadores administrativos. Concluímos que a satisfação no trabalho é afetada pela função profissional nos trabalhadores administrativos e pelo stress no trabalho nos trabalhadores administrativos.

Palavras-chave: Satisfação no trabalho, Qualidade de vida, Stress relacionado com o trabalho, Trabalhadores, Colaboradores.

1. Introduction

Job satisfaction has been identified as a pivotal factor in the realm of occupational health and performance, exerting a substantial influence on various aspects of organizational success. This notion has garnered significant attention within the domains of occupational psychology and human resource management due to its profound impact on key indicators such as work engagement, productivity, and retention rates (Rowan et al., 2022). The literature suggests that a workforce characterized by job satisfaction tends to demonstrate heightened levels of motivation, reduced absenteeism, and enhanced mental and physical well-being. These factors, in turn, contribute positively to both individual and organizational outcomes. However, the factors influencing job satisfaction can vary significantly depending on the nature of the work and the occupational group to which an individual belongs (Specchia et al., 2021).

One of the fundamental distinctions in the workforce is between blue-collar and white-collar employees. Blue-collar workers' job satisfaction may be influenced by various factors, including communication, stress levels, and motivational elements (Reig-Botella et al., 2022). On the other hand, job satisfaction in white-collar workers may be influenced by salary, supervision, and work environment. Studies show that job satisfaction among white-collar workers can affect organizational performance. It is imperative to comprehend these distinctions in order to formulate targeted workplace interventions that are designed to enhance job satisfaction among diverse occupational groups (Eriş & Kökalan, 2022).

Job satisfaction may also be influenced by a number of factors, including work role function, stress levels, and quality of life. Work role function, which reflects an individual's ability to meet job demands effectively, plays a significant role in shaping job satisfaction, particularly among workers whose tasks require high physical or cognitive effort (van Dijk et al., 2022). Stress, in both physical and psychological forms, has been identified as a significant predictor of diminished job satisfaction, often leading to consequences such as burnout, decreased motivation, and diminished job performance (Li et al., 2022). Furthermore, the quality of life, incorporating both physical and mental well-being, has been identified as a crucial factor influencing employees' work experiences, productivity, and satisfaction (Barmanpek et al., 2022).

Despite the extensive literature on job satisfaction, limited research has explored the interrelationships between work role function, stress, and quality of life in both blue-collar and white-collar workers using advanced statistical methods such as structural equation modeling (SEM). Based on this evidence, we attempted to extend these findings by examining the relationships between job satisfaction and work role function, stress, and quality of life of blue-collar and white-collar workers with structural equation modeling.

2. Literature Review

Employees are generally categorized as blue-collar and white-collar workers based on the nature of their jobs. Blue-collar work typically involves non-supervisory and non-managerial tasks, with employees often receiving an hourly wage (Kauhanen & Napari, 2012). These workers are frequently engaged in manual labour and are directly involved in the production process, which renders their work more tangible and easily observable. In contrast, white-collar work consists of data-driven tasks such as ideas, numbers, information, and figures (Schreurs et al., 2011). White-collar workers are non-manual employees who work in supervisory and administrative jobs. Presumably, internal labor markets and career concerns are more important for white-collar workers than for blue-

collar ones. Furthermore, the career paths of blue-collar workers are relatively limited (Schwerdt et al., 2010).

2.1. Job Related Stress

Stress is a pervasive challenge that many individuals encounter in the modern professional landscape (Hämmig et al., 2012). Occupational stress, also known as job-related stress, refers to psychological stress related to one's job and is considered a chronic condition (Basu et al., 2021). It arises when job requirements do not align with a worker's capabilities, resources, or needs. Both employees and employers are concerned about occupational stress because it impacts employees' emotional well-being, physical health, and job performance (Soteriades et al., 2022). Experiencing job-related stress can manifest in a variety of symptoms, affecting an individual's physical, psychological, and behavioral states. Additionally, job-related stress can stem from various sources related to working conditions, management practices, and interpersonal relationships. These can be categorized into broad and specific stressors. The main areas that can lead to work-related stress if not properly managed are demands, control, support, relationships, role, and change (Restrepo & Lemos, 2021).

High levels of job stress can lead to poor work performance, counterproductive work behavior, higher absenteeism, and injury. Chronically high job stress diminishes a worker's quality of life and increases the cost of health benefits provided by the employer (Cohidon et al., 2020). Exposure to long working hours, operates through increased psycho-social occupational stress and is the occupational risk factor with the largest attributable burden of disease, causing an estimated 745,000 workers to die from ischemic heart disease and stroke events in 2016. High levels of stress are associated with substantial increases in health service utilization (Pega et al., 2021).

Job-related stress may manifest differently for blue-collar and white-collar workers, reflecting the distinct challenges associated with their occupations. Blue-collar workers, often engaged in manual labor or physical tasks, face stressors related to demanding physical exertion, workplace safety concerns, and sometimes irregular work schedules. The potential for injuries and the repetitive nature of some tasks can contribute to long-term stress (Kajitani, 2015). Chronic workplace stress can significantly impact a blue-collar worker's physical and mental health (Kabir-Mokamelkhah et al., 2016). Compared to white-collar workers, blue-collar workers may exhibit more behavioral effects of stress due to communication issues or conflicts with supervisors. Data from the CDC indicates that blue-collar workers are at a higher risk of suicide compared to white-collar workers. Construction and extraction workers, as well as those in mining, quarrying, oil, and gas, have the highest suicide rates among all occupations, potentially linked to low-skilled work, lower education levels, and lower socioeconomic status (Peterson et al., 2020).

On the other hand, white-collar workers engaged in office-based professions may experience stress arising from deadlines and performance expectations. A study by the U.S. Bureau of Labor Statistics indicated that white-collar jobs were associated with a considerably higher level of psychological stress (U.S. Department of Labor, 1999). Sales and technical support roles had the highest stress levels, followed by managerial and professional positions. Factors contributing to stress in these roles may include expectations to work during off-hours, poor physical fitness, intense supervision, and threats of job loss. White-collar workers may also struggle with the challenges of maintaining a work-life balance, navigating office politics, and dealing with the pressure to

adapt to rapidly changing work environments. The effect of work-related stress may extend beyond the workplace, affecting overall well-being and potentially leading to physical and mental health issues (U.S. Department of Labor, 1999; Lips-Wiersma et al., 2016).

2.2. Work Role Function

The capacity of a worker to fulfill various job demands while considering their current state of health is referred to as their work role function. Work role function encompasses the duties, tasks, and responsibilities assigned to an employee within an organization. It defines what an employee is expected to accomplish in their position, clarifying expectations, assigning tasks, and evaluating performance. Defining clear roles is a basic element of organization and productivity, giving each employee a part in work processes (Dijk et al., 2022). Work role functions provide clarity in defining specific roles within the organization, helping employees understand their responsibilities and how they contribute to the overall goals. Work role functions must also align with laws to prevent discrimination and provide reasonable accommodations (Tampi et al., 2022).

Nowadays, the issue of reduced work role function has gained societal attention. This may occur when employees, despite being at their workplace, experience lower productivity due to health or work-related issues. The factors contributing to diminished work output encompass a range of conditions, such as stress, depression, job type, and work hours (Abma et al., 2018). In the literature, there was a connection between substandard work functioning and insomnia symptoms observed in both blue-collar and white-collar workers involved in construction and civil engineering work. Furthermore, shift work participation among blue-collar workers was associated with decreased work functioning (Kayaba et al., 2021).

2.3. The Quality of Life of Workers

Quality of Life (QOL) is a broad concept that encompasses an individual's overall well-being, satisfaction, and ability to participate in life events (Haraldstad et al., 2019). The World Health Organization (WHO) defines QOL as an individual's perception of their position in life within their cultural and value systems, in relation to their goals, expectations, standards, and concerns (WHO, 2020). It is a subjective and multidimensional measure that includes various aspects of a person's life, such as health, relationships, material comforts, and emotional well-being. Common indicators influencing quality of life include wealth, employment, environment, physical and mental health, education, recreation and leisure time, social belonging, religious beliefs, safety, security, and freedom. QOL is also highly individual, with factors like good health, strong relationships, and a degree of comfort playing a significant role (Haraldstad et al., 2019).

The quality of life for blue-collar and white-collar workers can differ based on the nature of their occupations. Physical demands, education level, depression, and self-efficacy often affect the quality of life of blue-collar workers. Workplace safety, job security, and access to healthcare may play pivotal roles in determining the quality of life for these individuals (Hwang & Park, 2015). Blue-collar workers may face more severe health issues compared to white-collar workers, impacting their years of healthy life. For example, blue-collar workers are more likely to suffer from conditions like arthritis, which reduces their quality of life and work productivity (Colla et al., 2024). Studies also show that blue-collar workers with low back pain report a lower quality of life and higher job-related stress (Leivas et al., 2022).

In contrast, white-collar workers, who are employed in professional, managerial, or administrative roles, often face a different set of challenges, including the stress of deadlines, long working hours, and a sedentary lifestyle. Musculoskeletal discomfort, work-life imbalance, unhealthy diets, poor sleep, and work-related stress often affect the quality of life of white-collar workers (Andersen, 2024; Amatori et al., 2024). A complex interplay of occupational factors shapes the quality of life of individuals in different sectors of the workforce. Therefore, it is important to consider diverse aspects when assessing and addressing their quality of life (Ko et al., 2013; Andersen, 2024; Amatori et al., 2024).

2.4. Job Satisfaction

Employees are crucial elements of every industry, directly affecting the business's success. The workplace's success is determined by employees' motivation, job satisfaction, and commitment to the workplace. Job satisfaction is a person's feelings after comparing expected or desired and actual outcomes (Specchia et al., 2021). Job-related factors such as wages, nature of the job, working conditions, management policies and colleagues, and personal characteristics such as age, gender, education level, and psychology may affect job satisfaction. Researchers have found that job satisfaction predicts the quality of life as individuals strive to achieve their work goals and maintain motivation (Anjum and Parvez, 2013; Drobnič et al., 2010). Moreover, factors that may influence job satisfaction include job characteristics and workplace stress (Steyn & Vawda, 2014; van Hoffen et al., 2021).

The jobs of white-collar workers may often be more complex than those of blue-collar workers (Hu et al., 2010). Because of this complexity, white-collar workers may have more information and dimensions for evaluating various aspects of their job. In addition, the greater diversity in their tasks may lead white-collar workers to assess their job satisfaction differently or more diversely. Similarly, interactions of white-collar workers with colleagues in different positions may lead to more differentiated judgments about job satisfaction (Hu et al., 2010). Conversely, for blue-collar workers, whose jobs tend to be more routine and monotonous, differences in job satisfaction may be influenced by fewer factors (Reig-Botella et al., 2022). However, studies have shown that blue-collar workers are less satisfied than white-collar workers with various aspects of the job, such as salary, supervisors, and the job itself (de Freitas Cardoso et al., 2022). Based on this evidence, we attempted to extend these findings by examining the relationships between job satisfaction and work role function, stress, and quality of life of blue-collar and white-collar workers with structural equation modeling.

3. Method

In this study, utilizing structural equation models, we analyzed the effect of work role function and stress on job satisfaction and its interaction with quality of life from the perspective of blue-collar and white-collar workers. By identifying these relationships, we aim to provide a comprehensive understanding of the key determinants of job satisfaction. The following hypotheses analyzed (Figure 1):

- H1: Work role function is associated with job satisfaction.
- H2: Perceived stress is associated with job satisfaction.
- H3: Physical quality of life is associated with job satisfaction.
- H4: Mental quality of life is associated with job satisfaction.
- H5: Mental quality of life is associated with perceived stress.

H6: Physical quality of life is associated with work role function.
 H7: Mental quality of life is associated with work role function.

Figure 1: Hypothetical model.

The Ethics Committee of Hacettepe University approved the study protocol with approval number 431-2935.

3.1. Data and sample selection

We collected data between June 2023 and December 2023 through face-to-face interviews and self-administered questionnaires. We interviewed 350 workers in six public organizations in Turkey (183 blue-collar and 167 white-collar), determined by simple random sampling. The organizations were closely located in a large city center and permitted to interview their employees. The inclusion criteria were being 18–65 years of age, working full time as a blue- or white-collar worker, having been working continuously in the same organization for at least one year, and being able to understand and read the written national language. The study excluded four workers who refused to participate, four part-time workers, two individuals who had worked in the same institution for less than a year, and three seasonal workers. We conducted interviews with a total of 337 individuals, comprising 175 blue-collar and 162 white-collar workers, who met the inclusion criteria. The blue-collar workers included in our study were crafts workers. White-collar workers were engineers. After obtaining written informed consent participants completed the questionnaires in paper format during the face-to-face interviews, where researchers provided instructions and clarified any questions.

3.2 Measures

Participants completed a demographic information form (age, gender, education level, period of employment at the workplace, unemployment experience, job duties, etc.), the Short Form-12 health survey (Ware et al., 1996), the Perceived Stress Scale (Cohen et al., 1983), the Work Role Function Questionnaire (Irmak et al., 2011) and the Minnesota Satisfaction Questionnaire (Weiss, 1967).

Short Form-12 Health Survey (SF-12). The SF-12 is a 12-item scale commonly used to assess health-related quality of life. Of the 12 items, one was for general health, two for

physical function, three for physical problems, two for restrictions on activities at home or work due to emotional problems, three for mental health, and one for social function and interaction restrictions. SF-12 has two dimensions: physical (PCS) and mental component summaries (MCS). Both scores range from 0 to 100, and a higher score indicates a better quality of life (Ware et al., 1996). Soylu and Kütük (2021) reported a validity and reliability study of the Turkish SF-12 Survey.

Perceived Stress Scale (PSS). Cohen first developed this scale in 1983 with 14 questions (Cohen et al., 1983) and removed four items in 1988 after an exploratory factor analysis (Cohen, 1988). The Turkish version was obtained from the final version, which included ten questions (Erci, 2006). This scale evaluates the perceived stress level in the last month by asking about feelings and thoughts. The total score ranges from 0 to 40. A high score indicates a high level of perceived stress. Erci reported the validity and reliability of the questionnaire in Turkish in 2006.

Work Role Function Questionnaire (WRFQ). This questionnaire evaluates the changes caused by physical health or emotional problems that limit daily working activities (Amick et al., 2000). WRFQ allows people to rate the perceived difficulty of doing their job. The questionnaire has five subscales: work scheduling demands, output demands, physical demands, mental demands, and social demands (Abma et al., 2018; Amick et al., 2000). Higher scores indicate better functioning in the work role. Irmak et al. reported the Turkish version of the questionnaire in 2011 (Irmak et al., 2011).

Minnesota Satisfaction Questionnaire (MSQ). This questionnaire was developed in 1967 by Weiss et al. and became a widely used questionnaire on job satisfaction. It has been developed to assess certain aspects of employee job satisfaction and provide information about the rewarding aspects of the job. The MSQ short form used in our study has 20 items and is scored between 20 and 100. As the score increases, job satisfaction increases (Martins & Proença, 2012). The Turkish version of the MSQ was published in 1985 by Baycan.

3.3 Data Analyses

Cronbach's alpha coefficients were used to test the internal consistency of the scales used in the analyses. We calculated the mean scores and standard deviations of the variables. Pearson correlation analysis was used to determine the relationship between variables. The SPSS 15.00 program was used in data analysis (Field, 2009). This old version was used due to institutional software availability at the time. However, the statistical methods applied (Cronbach's alpha, Pearson correlation, and descriptive analyses) are fundamental procedures that remain consistent across SPSS versions, ensuring that the results are not affected by the software version used.

To examine the effect of four variables (MCS, PCS, PSS, and WRFQ) on the job satisfaction of blue-collar and white-collar individuals, the AMOS 21 program and structural equation modeling were used. We used structural equation modeling, a comprehensive statistical method, to test models that contain hypotheses for causal and correlational relationships between observed and unobserved variables (Ullman & Bentler, 2012).

To evaluate model fit, we used various goodness-of-fit indices, each of which has a set of limit values for model acceptance. These are Chi-square (χ^2) Goodness of Fit Tests, Root Mean Square Error of Approximation (RMSEA), Goodness of Fit Index (GFI), Comparative Fit Index (CFI), and Normed Fit Index (NFI) values, and these indices were calculated in our study. For the predicted model to be accepted as suitable for the

database, a χ^2/df ratio of 2 is considered a good fit, and values up to 5 are considered adequate. In addition, CFI, GFI, and NFI values should be above 0.90, and the RMSEA value should be 0.05 and below (Ullman & Bentler, 2012).

We interpreted the effect sizes of the coefficients using the critical values for the standardized coefficients. We interpreted values less than 0.10 as a small effect, values around 0.30 as a medium effect, and values above 0.50 as a high effect (Ullman & Bentler, 2012).

4. Results

The mean age of the participants was $34 \pm 8,9$ years. Thirty-eight of them were women, and 270 of them were married. Information on the demographic characteristics of the participants is given in Table 1.

Table 1: Demographical characteristics

	Total (n=337)		White-collar (n=162)		Blue-collar (n=175)	
Age (year)	A=34,00 SD=8,97 (18-60)		A=33,00 SD=9,37 (18-60)		A=35,00 SD=7,65 (18-59)	
	n	n	%	n	%	
Gender						
Male	299	127	78%	172	98%	
Female	38	35	22%	3	2%	
Marital status						
Single	60	30	19%	30%	17%	
Married	270	127	78%	143%	82%	
Divorced	7	5	3%	2%	1%	
Educational status						
High school	143	9	5%	134	76%	
University	170	146	90%	24	14%	
MSc	24	24	15%	-		
Position						
Official	159	110	68%	49	28%	
Director*	40	35	22%	5	3%	
Employed	138	1	10%	121	69%	
Period of employment at the workplace						
1	30	12	8%	18	11%	
2-5	107	60	37%	47	27%	
6-10	63	25	15%	38	21%	
10-↑ (year)	137	65	40%	72	41%	
Unemployment before the current job						
Yes	210	107	66%	103	59%	
No	127	55	34%	72	41%	

Legend:

A= Average; SD= Standard Deviation; n= number of participants; MSc= Master of Science.

*Director of blue-collar workers were responsible for overseeing their fellow workers in the blue-collar category.

The number of items, mean scores, standard deviation values, and internal consistency coefficients (Cronbach's alpha values) of the scales were shown in Table 2. Accordingly, WRFQ, MSQ, PSS, and SF-12 PCS and MCS Cronbach's alpha values were .90, .91, .74 and .86/.90, respectively. All Cronbach's alpha values greater than .74 indicate that the scales are reliable (Table 2).

Table 2: Descriptive data for variables

		Mean	SD	Min	Max	Cronbach's alpha	Number of items
WRFQ	W	82,95	10,86	50,93	100	.90	27
	B	82,43	13,66	42,59	100		
MSQ	W	72,96	11,86	36	97	.91	20
	B	70,88	13,59	25	99		
PSS	W	14,21	5,32	0	29	.74	10
	B	15,78	4,44	0	30		
SF-12 PCS	W	48,72	6,30	28,10	60,80	.86	12
	B	49,15	7,17	23,10	62,70		
SF-12 MCS	W	47,61	8,93	19,90	66,70	.90	12
	B	46,37	8,80	20,50	61,20		

Legend:

WRFQ= Work Role Function Questionnaire; MSQ= Minnesota Satisfaction Questionnaire, PSS=Perceived Stress Scale; SF-12 PCS= Short Form-12 physical, SF-12 MCS= Short Form-12 mental, W=White-collar, B= Blue-collar.

According to Pearson Correlation Analysis, MSQ had a positive correlation with SF-12 PCS and MCS ($r=.15$, $r=.24$) and WRFQ ($r=.34$), and a negative correlation with PSS ($r=-.27$). SF-12 PCS and MCS had a positive correlation with WRFQ ($r=.25$, $r=.32$) and a negative correlation with PSS ($r=-.22$, $r=-.60$). There was a negative correlation between WRFQ and PSS ($r=-.32$) ($p<0.01$).

In the white-collar workers, MSQ had a positive correlation with SF-12 PCS and MCS ($r=.16$, $r=.29$) and WRFQ ($r=.27$), and a negative correlation with PSS ($r=-.38$). SF-12 PCS and MCS had a positive correlation with WRFQ ($r=.26$, $r=.38$) and a negative correlation with PSS ($r=-.19$, $r=-.71$). There was a negative correlation between WRFQ and PSS ($r=-.45$) ($p<0.05$).

In the blue-collar workers, MSQ had a positive correlation with SF-12 PCS and MCS ($r=.13$, $r=.21$) and WRFQ ($r=.45$), and a negative correlation with PSS ($r=-.20$). SF-12 PCS and MCS had a positive correlation with WRFQ ($r=.26$, $r=.39$) and a negative correlation with PSS ($r=-.27$, $r=-.49$). There was a negative correlation between WRFQ and PSS ($r=-.32$) ($p<0.05$) (Table 3).

Table 3: Inter-correlations for variables

Total group	WRFQ	MSQ	PSS	SF-12 PCS	SF-12 MCS
WRFQ	1	.346**	-.327**	.253**	.325**
MSQ		.000	.000	.000	.000
PSS		1	-.274**	.153**	.244**
SF-12 PCS			.000	.005	.000
SF-12 MCS			1	-.228**	-.609**
				.000	.000
				1	-.032
					.557
					1

White-collar	WRFQ	MSQ	PSS	SF-12 PCS	SF-12 MCS
WRFQ	1	.271** .001	-.451** .001	.260** .001	.388** .001
MSQ		1	-.381* .001	.167* .037	.295** .001
PSS			1	-.194* .015	-.715** .001
SF-12 PCS				1	-.023 .778
SF-12 MCS					1
Blue-collar	WRFQ	MSQ	PSS	SF-12 PCS	SF-12 MCS
WRFQ	1	.454** .001	-.326** .001	.261** .001	.394** .001
MSQ		1	-.205** .008	.135 .081	.218** .004
PSS			1	-.279** .001	-.493** .001
SF-12 PCS				1	-.038 .625
SF-12 MCS					1

Legend:

**p<.01, *p<.05, n=337

WRFQ= Work Role Function Questionnaire-27; MSQ= Minnesota Satisfaction Questionnaire, PSS=Perceived Stress Scale; SF-12 PCS= Short Form-12 physical, SF-12 MCS= Short Form-12 mental.

At the final stage of the analysis, we analysed the model using the structural equation approach. While testing the hypothesis of the study with the analysis, it was also aimed at determining the most appropriate model that explains the existing interactions. The results of the model created to determine the effect of work role function and stress on job satisfaction and the interaction with quality of life according to blue-collar and white-collar workers are shown in Table 4, and graphics are shown in Figures 2 and 3. In Table 4, the AMOS program provided various compliance statistics based on different criteria. The chi-square value in the table denotes the discrepancy. The χ^2 value of the model = 4,069. The degree of freedom is a critical criterion in the χ^2 test. In cases where the degrees of freedom are large, the chi-square value tends to give meaningful results. For this reason, the ratio of the chi-square value to the degrees of freedom (χ^2/df) is accepted as a criterion. The degrees of freedom of the models were 3.19 and 0.5. RMSEA values were 0.11 and 0. Other model evaluation criteria in Table 5 reveal promising results for our model (CFI=0.99, 0.97, NFI=0.99, 0.96, AGFI=0.98, 0.88). In general, the model fits the data according to the goodness-of-fit indices.

Table 4: Result from structural equation modeling

Goodness-of-fit indices	White collar	Blue collar	Standard values
χ^2/df	3.194	0.525	<5
GFI	0.98	0.99	>.90
RMSEA	0.11	0.00	<.05
CFI	0.97	0.99	>.90
NFI	0.96	0.99	>.90
AGFI	0.88	0.98	>.90

According to the findings in Table 5 and Figures 2 and 3, mental quality of life (MCS) increased WRFQ (bc=.60, wc=.42) and decreased PSS (bc=.26, wc=.43) and physical quality of life (PCS) increased WRFQ (bc=.60, wc=.43) in both groups. In addition, WRFQ increased MSQ (bc=.38) in blue-collar workers, and PSS decreased MSQ (wc=.60) in white-collar workers.

Table 5: Coefficients of the model according to the structural equation models

			White collar		Blue collar	
			Estimate	P	Estimate	P
SF-12/MCS	→	WRFQ	0.423	<.001 **	0.608	<.001 **
SF-12/PCS	→	PSS	-0.188	<.001 **	-0.181	<.001 **
SF-12/MCS	→	PSS	-0.432	<.001 **	-0.260	<.001 **
SF-12/PCS	→	WRFQ	0.436	.004 *	0.605	<.001 **
SF-12/MCS	→	MSQ	0.097	.498	0.082	.540
SF-12/PCS	→	MSQ	0.187	.202	0.054	.714
WRFQ	→	MSQ	0.074	.302	0.385	<.001 **
PSS	→	MSQ	-0.607	.010 *	-0.033	.897

Legend:

** $p < .01$, * $p < .05$,

WRFQ= Work Role Function Questionnaire-27; MSQ= Minnesota Satisfaction Questionnaire, PSS=Perceived Stress Scale;

SF-12 PCS= Short Form-12 physical, SF-12 MCS= Short Form-12 mental.

Figure 2: Model for white-collar workers.

Figure 3: Model for blue-collar workers.

5. Discussion

In this study, we conducted an in-depth examination of the complex relationships between job satisfaction, work role function, stress, and quality of life among both white-collar and blue-collar workers. By employing structural equation modelling, we were able to uncover the distinct factors that contribute to job satisfaction within each group. We determined that work role function in blue-collar workers and stress in white-collar workers affected job satisfaction. Based on these results, it can be inferred that white-collar

workers are more likely to achieve higher levels of job satisfaction when they experience reduced levels of stress. In contrast, blue-collar workers tend to experience greater job satisfaction when they encounter fewer difficulties or challenges in fulfilling their job responsibilities. This suggests that by addressing these specific factors - minimizing stress for white-collar workers and reducing job-related obstacles for blue-collar workers - employers can foster a more positive and satisfying work environment for both groups.

We used the structural equation model to examine the hypothesis model. The fit indexes showed that the model explained correlations between measurements. According to the structural equation model results, work role function in white-collar and blue-collar workers was defined by the physical and mental quality of life. Furthermore, the mental quality of life in both worker groups accounted for stress. These results imply that workers with a high quality of life will have a lower perceived difficulty in doing their job, and workers with a high mental quality of life will have less stress. Our findings are supported by studies stating that work-related stress affects quality of life and job satisfaction (Tsai, 2012; Roelen et al., 2014). In our study, we evaluated white-collar and blue-collar workers' health-related quality of life. Health-related quality of life reflects a person's perception of their health and is considered to be a broad measure of health status. In our study, unlike other studies, we wanted to examine the effect of a person's perception of health-related quality of life on job satisfaction rather than the factors affecting quality of life. We did not find a direct effect of health-related quality of life on job satisfaction. The health conditions of the workers we included in the study may have contributed to this. In the literature, it has been reported that conditions such as cardiovascular diseases, insomnia, and low back pain have a negative impact on the quality of life of workers (Kayaba et al., 2021; Hwang & Park, 2015). Therefore, future studies should closely examine workers' health status and the impact of health on job satisfaction.

Work-related stress is known to cause mental illnesses like depression, which may also have an impact on job satisfaction (Wu et al., 2011). As a result of the structural equation modelling, we determined that stress reduces job satisfaction in white-collar workers. The difference between the two groups in terms of the effect of stress on job satisfaction is that the mental workload, having too much responsibility, and career concerns that may increase stress in white-collar workers may be greater than those of blue-collar workers (Schwerdt et al., 2010). Organizational psychosocial interventions focusing on enhancing social support and rewards may have the potential to mitigate stress among white-collar workers (Gilbert-Ouimet et al., 2015).

Unlike white-collar workers, blue-collar workers' job satisfaction is explained by their work role function. Blue-collar workers rely more on their physical abilities in their occupations compared to white-collar workers. As a result, the physical capacities of male blue-collar workers tend to decline more rapidly than those of their white-collar workers¹¹). In addition, blue-collar workers generally work in more difficult conditions than white-collar workers due to factors such as long working hours and the physical working environment (Schreurs et al., 2011; Schwerdt et al., 2010; Wong et al., 2019). The literature also asserts that blue-collar workers place less value on realizing their full potential and serving others than do white-collar workers (Lips-Wiersma et al., 2016). Moreover, blue-collar workers may have less motivating job characteristics than white-collar workers (Huang, 2011). Therefore, the perceived difficulty in doing their job as blue-collar workers may have affected their job satisfaction.

5.1. Limitations and Future Research

It is important to acknowledge the limitations of our study, particularly in relation to its cross-sectional design. Although cross-sectional studies offer valuable insights into the factors influencing job satisfaction at a specific point in time, they are not well-suited to examining how these factors may evolve or change over time. Consequently, the capacity to infer causal relationships between variables is constrained. To gain a more comprehensive understanding of the factors that contribute to job satisfaction, future research should incorporate longitudinal studies, which would enable a more in-depth examination of how job satisfaction is influenced by various factors across different time periods and stages of workers' careers.

Furthermore, an additional limitation of our study is the unequal distribution of male and female workers within our sample. The discrepancy in the number of male and female participants may have constrained our capacity to comprehensively evaluate the influence of gender on job satisfaction. Gender can be a significant factor in shaping workers' experiences, expectations, and satisfaction levels in the workplace. The imbalance in our sample may have hindered our ability to accurately capture this dynamic. It is therefore recommended that future research should aim to include more balanced samples of male and female workers in order to provide a more nuanced understanding of how gender influences job satisfaction in both blue-collar and white-collar workers. It would be particularly beneficial to conduct studies that focus specifically on gender differences in job satisfaction, given the distinct challenges and opportunities that male and female workers may face in different work environments.

Moreover, our study does not examine certain environmental factors that could potentially influence job satisfaction among workers, such as the geographical location of the workplace or the surrounding physical and social environment. The blue-collar and white-collar workers included in the study were all employed in a large city centre, where the environmental characteristics of their workplaces were relatively similar. Nevertheless, it is possible that job satisfaction may vary considerably in different settings, for example between rural and urban environments or between industries located in disparate geographic regions. Further research should investigate these environmental factors in greater depth, as they may exert a pivotal influence on workers' overall job satisfaction.

A further area meriting investigation is the distinction between job characteristics in public and private sector employment. The present study did not address this distinction directly; however, it is a possibility that job satisfaction may differ significantly between workers in these two sectors due to variations in job security, benefits, and organisational culture. It would be beneficial for future studies to consider exploring the public-private sector divide in both blue-collar and white-collar workers, with the aim of gaining a deeper understanding of how sector-specific job characteristics influence job satisfaction. This could provide a more detailed and comprehensive account of the factors affecting job satisfaction across different types of employment and work environments.

6. Conclusion

This study offers a comprehensive understanding of the multifaceted factors that influence job satisfaction, including stress levels, work role function, and quality of life, as they impact both blue-collar and white-collar workers. The application of a structural equation model enabled the identification of distinctive patterns in the drivers of job satisfaction for these two groups. In particular, the findings revealed that job satisfaction

among blue-collar workers is primarily shaped by their work role function. This suggests that the way they perceive and fulfil their roles within the workplace is a pivotal determinant of their overall job satisfaction. Conversely, stress was identified as the primary factor influencing job satisfaction among white-collar workers, underscoring the distinctive pressures and challenges encountered by individuals in these roles.

It is noteworthy that while a direct influence of quality of life on both stress levels and work role function was observed across both groups, a direct link between quality of life and job satisfaction itself could not be established. This indicates that job satisfaction is a complex and multifaceted construct, which cannot be attributed to a single factor. Rather, it is shaped by a variety of interrelated factors, each of which contributes to different aspects of overall job satisfaction. Job satisfaction is a complex and nuanced concept, encompassing satisfaction with various distinct facets of a person's work experience.

Furthermore, our findings highlight the necessity of acknowledging the potential for divergence in the perspectives and priorities of blue-collar and white-collar workers about their respective roles. Such discrepancies are likely attributable to the intrinsic characteristics of the work itself, as well as the distinctive challenges and rewards associated with each role. Consequently, as conducted in this study, an examination of job satisfaction patterns separately for these two groups permits a more detailed comprehension of the elements that contribute to job satisfaction. Such an approach may enable the acquisition of valuable insights into the distinctive needs and experiences of both blue-collar and white-collar workers, thereby enhancing our understanding of the complex nature of job satisfaction across different work environments.

7. References

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